

STUDY ON NEW SURFACE PRETREATMENTS OF PAINTING TO CFRP LAMINATES

T. Suzuki¹, H. Hira^{2*}

¹ Aichi Science and Technology Foundation, Toyota, Japan

² School of Engineering, Daido University, Nagoya, Japan

* Corresponding author (hira-h@daido-it.ac.jp)

Keywords: *CFRP, surface pretreatment, painting, ozone, laser*

1 Introduction

Carbon fiber reinforced polymer composites (CFRPs) have become of great interest in the last decades. CFRPs have been widely used in many engineering fields such as aerospace, automobiles, bridge supports, buildings, chemical reactor vessels, ships, and trains because of their high strength-to-weight and stiffness-to-weight ratios [1-3].

At manufacturing operations of CFRPs, release agents are essentially vital to protect mold and part from damage by unwanted adhesion [4]. Release agents, which may contain polymeric fluorinated hydrocarbons and/or silicones, are generally applied directly to the mold, and the prepared CFRP part is eventually coated with the release agents. However residues of release agents contaminate the surface of the CFRP part, which hinder durable adhesion and painting [5]. Surface pretreatments of CFRPs are, therefore, very important issues to apply the post-processes. Sanding as one of the conventional methods is, however, both cost and time consumptive works.

In this study, new surface pretreatment methods of painting to CFRPs, ozone exposure and YAG laser irradiation techniques, are investigated. It has been reported that ozone exposure and laser irradiation procedures are effective methods of removing a variety of contaminants of surfaces [6-8]. It is expected these techniques can remove the release agent from the surfaces of the CFRP laminates, which provides improved painting properties.

2 Experimental

2.1 Materials

Two kinds of flat CFRP laminates (Epoxy/CF (Toho Tenax Co., Ltd.) and Polyphenylene sulfide (PPS)/CF (TenCate Advanced Composites)) were used;

a) Epoxy/CF

- Matrix: Epoxy#135, CF: UTS50 12K
- Resin content: 45 %
- Lay-up sequence pattern: {(±45)/0.90}1S
- Thickness: 1.63 mm (8 ply)
- Release agent: silicone

a) PPS/CF

- Matrix: PPS, CF: T300J 3K
- Resin content: 50 %
- Lay-up sequence pattern: (0.90)5
- Thickness: 1.37 mm (5 ply)
- Release agent: unknown

2.2 Surface pretreatments

New two methods, ozone exposure and weak laser beam irradiation, and conventional sanding were examined. Ozone exposure experiment was carried out by a SGA series ozonizer (Sumitomo Precision Products Co., Ltd) with the ozone concentration of 0.5 or 10 %. Fig. 1 shows overview and schematic representation of the ozone exposure equipment. YAG laser irradiation technique was performed with a YLR-5000C2 unit (Laser X Co., Ltd). The YAG laser beam oscillated certain amplitude perpendicular to the direction of travel was irradiated and scanned test panel (Fig. 2). #150, #240, and #600 count sandpapers were used to conventional handwork surface abrasion.

2.3 Measurements

Surface roughness of the CFRP laminates were measured by a SurfTest SV-2000 (Mitutoyo Corp). X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) measurements were carried out by an AXIS-His (Shimadzu Corp.) using Al-K α radiation source. Painting properties of the CFRP laminates were conducted as follows: Sky Hullo primer #5000 (Nihon Tokushu Toryo Co., Ltd.) was sprayed onto the CFRPs with an air brush. After that, Sky Hullo

Fig. 1 Photographs and schematic diagram of ozone exposure equipment; (a) Overview, (b) sample chamber, and (c) schematic diagram [(1) PSA ozonizer, (2) air feed, (3) humidity controller, (4) air pump, (5) ozone concentration monitor, (6) sample chamber, and (7) ozone killer].

topcoat #400 (Nihon Tokushu Toryo Co., Ltd.) was painted onto the primer-coated CFRPs with an air brush. Adhesion performance of paint layer was evaluated via the tape test according to the guideline of the Japanese Industrial Standards Committee (JIS K5600-5-6). The cross-hatched cuts with 2 mm apart were made on the painting layer by a razor

Fig. 2 Photograph of YAG laser irradiation experiment.

blade to form 25 of small squares. After that, scotch tape was applied to the small squares and peeled off. The number of the small squares kept on the CFRP laminate was counted.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Morphological properties

Figs. 3 and 4 show CCD microscope images of the Epoxy/CF and PPS/CF laminates exposed to ozone atmosphere, respectively. For the Epoxy/CF, surface epoxy matrix is decomposed by the ozone exposure and surface roughness is slightly increased with increasing concentration of ozone atmosphere (Fig. 3), and no degradation is found inside. At the exposure of 0.5% of ozone atmosphere, liquid-like decomposed product appears on the surface of the Epoxy/CF, and the decomposed product can be easily wiped off. On the other hand, at the exposure of 10% of ozone atmosphere, powder-like decomposed product deposits on the surface area.

Fig. 3 Top view of the Epoxy/CF laminate exposed to (a) 0.5 % of ozone atmosphere for 2 h and (b) 10 % of ozone atmosphere for 2 h.

Fig. 4 Cross-sectional view of the PPS/CF laminate exposed to (a) 0.5 % of ozone atmosphere for 2 h and (b) 10 % of ozone atmosphere for 4 h.

The reason of the difference in the states of decomposed products resulting from 0.5 % and 10 % of ozone exposures is under consideration.

For the PPS/CF laminate, visible decomposition at surface PPS matrix cannot be found, whereas micro-cracks are formed and the micro-cracks are propagated from surface region to inside with increasing concentration of ozone atmosphere (Fig. 4). The micro-cracks might be brought by release of residual stress which would be stored at production process of the PPS/CF laminate.

YAG laser irradiation for the CFRPs also provides decompositions of the matrices. Fig. 5 provides surface appearance of Epoxy/CF and PPS/CF laminates pretreated by the YAG laser irradiation.

Increased laser power, however, results in considerably damaged and roughened surface.

Surface atomic compositions of surface-pretreated CFRPs were investigated by XPS measurements. Fig. 6 represents XPS spectra of surface-pretreated Epoxy/CF laminates. It is found the peaks assigned to Si are found on the as-received laminate (Fig. 6(a)) because of the existence of a silicone-type release agent [9]. As shown in Fig. 6(b), for conventional handwork sanding, the Si peaks are disappeared, which indicates the release agent is successfully removed. For 10% of ozone exposure, however, the Si peaks are still remained (Fig. 6(c)), whereas the peaks are disappeared for 0.5% of ozone exposure (data not shown). The discrepancy might

Fig. 5 Surface appearance of Epoxy/CF and PPS/CF laminates pretreated by YAG laser irradiation.

be related to the difference in the states of decomposed products above mentioned. For 10% of ozone exposure, powder-like decomposed product which contains release agent cannot be completely blown out after ozone exposure experiment, and the release agent is still remained on the roughened surface of the Epoxy/CF laminate. On the other hand, for 0.5% of ozone exposure, liquid-like decomposed product can be easily wiped off, and release agent is simultaneously removed from the surface of the Epoxy/CF. The Epoxy/CF laminate pretreated by YAG laser irradiation also shows the Si peaks (Fig. 6(d)). There are two possible hypotheses to explain the existence of the Si peaks. One is that Si or release agent has initially penetrated in the certain depth of inner epoxy matrix at the curing process to form the CFRP laminate. Another is that Si-contained decomposed product evaporated by the laser irradiation adsorbs again on the surface after passing the laser.

Fig. 7 shows XPS spectra of surface-pretreated PPS/CF laminates. Small peaks assigned to Si are found for the as-received PPS/CF surface (Fig. 7(a)). Although there are no information about release

agent used for the manufacturing process of the PPS/CF laminate, this result suggests the existence of a silicone-type release agent on the surface. As shown in Figs. 7(b) – (d), the Si peaks are disappeared by handwork sanding, ozone exposure, and YAG laser irradiation techniques, indicating that the release agent is successfully removed from the surface of the PPS/CF laminate. It is also pointed out that the effects of surface pretreatments with ozone exposure and laser irradiation for the PPS/CF laminate are somewhat different from those for the Epoxy/CF laminate.

3.2 Paint adhesion test

Surface roughness and adhesion performance of painting layer of the surface-pretreated CFRPs are summarized in Table 1.

3.2.1 Epoxy/CF laminates

For the handwork sanding, smaller count or more coarse-grid sandpaper provides more roughened surface. It is found for the ozone exposure that surface roughness is slightly increased with increasing concentration of ozone atmosphere. YAG laser irradiation brings about highly roughened

Fig. 6 XPS spectra of surface-pretreated Epoxy/CF laminate; (a) as-received, (b) handwork sanding (#240), (c) ozone exposure (10% of ozone atmosphere for 2h), and (d) YAG laser irradiation (0.36 mJ/cm²). The asterisks (*) are assigned to extraneous elements contaminated during ozone exposure and YAG laser irradiation experiments.

surface, and the surface roughness is considerably increased with increasing energy density. All small painting squares coated on the as-received Epoxy/CF laminate are peeled off by the tape test because of the existing of release agent. This result means poor painting adhesion of the as-received Epoxy/CF laminate. The Epoxy/CF laminate pretreated with sandpapers have good adhesion of the paint layer. Considering the results of XPS analyses, it can be deduced that the good adhesion property is brought by successful removing of release agent. On the other hand, the Epoxy/CF laminates pretreated with ozone exposure and YAG laser irradiation at moderate conditions show poor adhesion. The poor adhesion properties might be brought by both less of surface roughness and

insufficient removal of release agent. Whereas 0.5% of ozone atmosphere for 10 h and 0.50 mJ/m² of YAG laser irradiation, which are relatively hard conditions, induce improved paint adhesion.

3.2.2 PPS/CF laminates

As similar to the Epoxy/CF laminates, more coarse-grid sandpaper provides more roughened surface for the handwork sanding. Ozone exposure and YAG laser irradiation also bring about increased surface roughness with increasing concentration of ozone atmosphere and energy density, respectively. The as-received PPS/CF laminate also shows poor adhesion properties as similar to the as-received Epoxy/CF laminate above mentioned. This fact again indicates the existence of release agent on the surface although there are no detailed information

Fig. 7 XPS spectra of surface-pretreated PPS/CF laminate; (a) as-received, (b) handwork sanding (#240), (c) ozone exposure (10% of ozone atmosphere for 2h), and (d) YAG laser irradiation (0.36 mJ/cm²).

about the release agent used for the manufacturing process of the PPS/CF laminate. Handwork sanding with #240 or #600 count sandpaper results in poor adhesion, whereas the sanding with #150 count sandpaper provides good adhesion. The poor adhesion for the sanding with fine-grid sandpapers might be considered to be due to a difficulty of sufficient handwork sanding to remove release agent owing to hard PPS matrix. It is worth noting for the PPS/CF laminate that paint adhesion property is improved by not only ozone exposure but also YAG laser irradiation carried out at various conditions. The good adhesion property is brought by efficient removing of release agent, which is consistent with the results of XPS analyses. Especially for the ozone exposure, it is considered that an anchor effect brought by the surface micro-cracks also contributes

to the improvement of paint adhesion. These facts mean that ozone exposure and laser irradiation techniques are applicable for the improvement of painting property of the PPS/CF laminate.

4 Conclusions

Novel surface pretreatment methods of painting to Epoxy/CF and PPS/CF laminates, ozone exposure and YAG laser irradiation techniques were investigated. The main results obtained are shown below.

- 1) Ozone exposure and YAG laser irradiation bring about increased surface roughness of the laminates with increasing concentration of ozone atmosphere and energy density, respectively. In

particular, ozone exposure at 0.5% of ozone atmosphere for 10 h provides preferable surface roughness – adhesion relationship.

2) In the case of the Epoxy/CF, conventional handwork sanding can successfully remove the surface release agent, which leads to improved paint adhesion. On the other hand, the Epoxy/CF pretreated with ozone exposure and YAG laser irradiation at moderate conditions show poor adhesion. The poor adhesion properties might be brought by both less of surface roughness and insufficient removal of release agent.

3) For the PPS/CF, handwork sanding with #150 count of coarse-grid sandpaper provides good adhesion. Ozone exposure and YAG laser irradiation carried out at various conditions also brings about improved paint adhesion, indicating efficient removing of release agent. Especially for the ozone exposure, it is considered that an anchor effect brought by the surface micro-cracks also contributes to the improvement of paint adhesion.

It is concluded that the ozone exposure and YAG laser irradiation techniques are applicable for the

Table 1 Surface pretreatment conditions and adhesion property of paint to the CFRP laminates

CFRP	Pretreatment	Condition	Surface roughness [μm]	Adhesion property ¹⁾
Epoxy/CF	as-received	–	0.25	0 / 25
	sandpaper	#600	0.30	24 / 25
		#240	0.51	25 / 25
		#150	0.81	25 / 25
	ozone exposure	10 %, 2 h	0.38	0 / 25
		0.5 %, 2h	0.38	0 / 25
		0.5 %, 10h	0.32	17 / 25
	YAG laser	0.36 mJ/cm ²	1.6	9 / 25
		0.50 mJ/cm ²	7.4	23 / 25
	PPS/CF	as-received	–	0.47
sandpaper		#600	0.57	1 / 25
		#240	0.71	3 / 25
		#150	1.3	23 / 25
ozone exposure		10 %, 2 h	0.78	22 / 25
		0.5 %, 2h	0.58	25 / 25
		0.5 %, 10h	0.42	25 / 25
YAG laser		0.36 mJ/cm ²	3.0	20 / 25
		0.50 mJ/cm ²	4.0	25 / 25

1) {Number of small squares kept on the CFRP laminate after the tape test} / 25.

improvement of painting properties of CFRP laminates, which is especially effective for the PPS/CF. It is expected that the ozone exposure and YAG laser irradiation techniques are widely applied for other CFRPs by optimization of treatment conditions and these techniques are extensively contribute to advanced automatization and productivity improvement for CFRP industries.

Acknowledgement

This work was supported by “Knowledge Hub Aichi Priority Research Project”. The authors wish to thank Kawasaki Heavy Industries, Ltd. for providing the Epoxy/CF laminate.

References

- [1] B. Fernández, F. Mujika, A. D. Benito and I. Mondragon, “Mechanical characterization of woven carbon fiber composites with poly(methyl methacrylate)- modified epoxy matrices”, *Polym. Comp.*, Vol. 24, No. 5, pp 640-654, 2003.
- [2] E. T. Thostenson, C. Li and T. W. Chou, “Nanocomposites in context”, *Comp. Sci. Technol.*, Vol 65, pp 491-516, 2005.
- [3] D.A. Papargyris, R.J. Day, A. Nesbitt and D. Bakavos “Comparison of the mechanical and physical properties of a carbon fibre epoxy composite manufactured by resin transfer moulding using conventional and microwave heating”. *Compos. Sci. Technol.*, Vol. 68, Issues 7-8, pp 1854-1861, 2008.
- [4] A. B. Strong, “*Fundamentals of Composites Manufacturing – Materials, Methods, and Applications*”, 2nd edition, Society of Manufacturing Engineers, Dearborn, Michigan, 2008.
- [5] B. M. Parker and R. M. Waghorne “Surface pretreatment of carbon fiber-reinforced composites for adhesive bonding”. *Composites*, Vol. 13, Issue 3, pp 280-288, 1982.
- [6] J. R. Vig, “UV/ozone cleaning of surfaces”, *J. Vac. Sci. Technol. A*, Vol. 3, No. 3, pp 1027-1034, 1985.
- [7] H. Y. Nie, M. J. Walzak, B. Berno and N. S. McIntyre, “Atomic force microscopy study of polypropylene surfaces treated by UV and ozone exposure: modification of morphology and adhesion force”, *Appl. Surf. Sci.*, 144-145, pp 627-632, 1999.
- [8] R. E. Litchfield, G. W. Critchlow and S. Wilson, “Surface cleaning technologies for the removal of crosslinked epoxide resin” *Int. J. Adhesion & Adhesives*, Vol. 26, Issue 5, pp 295-303, 2006.
- [9] S. R. Dhakate, O. P. Bahl, “Effect of carbon fiber surface functional groups on the mechanical properties of carbon-carbon composites with HTT”, *Carbon*, Vol. 41, pp 1193-1203, 2003.